

New smut fungi (Ustilaginomycetes) from Thailand

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Abstract. Eight new smut fungi, collected in Thailand, are described: *Macalpinomyces siamensis* on *Coelorachis striata*, *Sporisorium clandestinum* on *Aristida setacea*, *S. pseudosorghii* on *Pseudosorghum fasciculare*, *S. trispicatae* on *Eulalia trispicata*, *Tilletia Chiangmaiensis* on *Arundinella bengalensis*, *T. filisora* on *Pennisetum setosum*, *T. lageniformis* on *Hyparrhenia rufa*, and *Yelsemia droserae* on *Drosera burmanni* and on *D. indica* (from Australia).

Key words: *Macalpinomyces*, new species, smut fungi, *Sporisorium*, Thailand, *Tilletia*, Ustilaginomycetes, *Yelsemia*

Introduction

The smut fungi of Thailand are poorly known. In the literature we found records of only 14 (+ 5 unidentified) smut fungi from Thailand. A survey for three weeks in December 2005, resulted in 65 smut fungus collections, representing 41 species (comp. also Shivas *et al.* in press). Of the collected specimens, eleven turned out to be new species, of which two *Tilletia thailandica* and *Ustilago planetella* both on *Eragrostis*, and one *Tilletia setariae-parviflorae* on *Setaria*, are described elsewhere (*Mycotaxon*, in work). Eight new species are described below.

Materials and Methods

Sorus and spore characteristics were studied using living and also dried specimens. For light microscopy (LM), spores were suspended in a droplet of lactophenol on a microscope slide, covered with a cover glass, and gently heated to boiling point. For scanning electron microscopy (SEM), dry spores were dusted on double-sided adhesive tape, mounted on a specimen stub, sputter-coated with gold-palladium, c. 20 nm,

and examined in a SEM at 10 kV. The collected specimens have been deposited in mycological herbaria. For acronyms see Holmgren *et al.* (1990). Additional herbaria are H.U.V. (Herbarium Ustilag. Vánky, Tübingen, Germany) and T.P.P.H. (Thai Plant Pathology Herbarium, Bangkok, Thailand).

Results

Coelorachis Brongn., with about 21 species throughout the tropics, belongs to the subfam. Panicoideae, tribe Andropogoneae, subtribe Rottboelliinae (Clayton & Renvoize 1986: 365). On *Coelorachis* one smut fungus is known, *Sporisorium coelorachidis* Vánky (2001: 292), type on *C. clarkei* (Hack.) Blatter & McCann., India. The host plant of another smut, *Sporisorium desertorum* (Thüm.) Vánky, described on *Coelorachis hirsuta* (Forssk.) Brongn., is a synonym of *Lasiurus indicus* Henrard. A smut fungus collected in Thailand on *Coelorachis striata* is a different and new species. It differs also from the six known smut fungi on the closely related host genera *Rhytachne* and *Phacelurus*, including *Jardinea* (comp. Vánky 2006: 38–41), as well as

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from the smut fungi on *Rottboellia*, *Eremochloa*, *Hackelochloa*, *Lasiurus*, and *Manisuris*.

Macalpinomyces siamensis R.G. Shivas, Vánky & Athipunyakom, **sp. nov.**

Typus in matrice Coelorachis striata (Nees ex Steud.) A. Camus, Thailand, Chiang Mai Prov., Phrao Distr., 53 km NE urbe Chiang Mai, 19°05'16.2" N, 99°05'43.0" E, alt. 538 m.s.m., 28.XII.2005, leg. R.G. Shivas, P. Athipunyakom, S. Likhitekaraj, W. Butranu, C. & K. Vánky. **Holotypus** in Herbario Ustil. Vánky, H.U.V. 21 194; **isotypus** in BRIP 47 765.

Sori in ovarii nonnullis inflorescentiae eiusdem, longe cylindrici, 1-2 × 10-20 mm, saepe arcuati vel torti, peridio origine nutritorio, crasso, hispido, primo viridi, serius brunneo cooperti, quo in maturitate longitudinaliter fisso massam atrobrunneam, semiagglutinatum usque pulveream sporarum et cellularum sterilium dispergentes. **Sporae** globosae, subglobosae usque late ellipsoidales, 6,5-9 × 7-9,5 μm, mediocriter atrolivaceobrunneae; pariete aequali, 0,5-1 μm crasso, spicis cca. 0,5 μm altis, 0,3-0,4 μm latis, moderate dense distributis; imago obliqua sporarum leniter serrulata. **Cellulae steriles** in turmis laxis, irregularibus, cellulae singulae globosae, subglobosae vel late ellipsoidales, magnitudine variae, 6,5-14,5 × 6,5-17 μm, subhyalinae; pariete aequali, cca. 0,5 μm crasso, levi, contentu homogeneo.

Sori (Fig. 1, Pl. Ia) in some ovaries of an inflorescence, long cylindrical, 1-2 × 10-20 mm, often bent or twisted, covered by a thick, hispid, first green later brown peridium of host origin which splits longitudinally at maturity, dispersing the dark brown, semiagglutinated to powdery mass of spores and sterile cells. **Spores** (Figs 4-5) globose, subglobose to broadly ellipsoidal, 6.5-9 × 7-9.5 μm, medium dark olivaceous brown; wall even, 0.5-1 μm thick, provided with moderately densely situated, c. 0.5 μm high, 0.3-0.4 μm wide spines, spore profile finely serrate. **Sterile cells** (Figs 4-5) in loose, irregular groups, single cells globose, subglobose or broadly ellipsoidal, varying in size, 6.5-14.5 × 6.5-17 μm, subhyaline; wall even, c. 0.5 μm thick, smooth, content homogenous.

On Poaceae: *Coelorachis striata* (Nees ex Steud.) A. Camus.

Distribution: SE Asia (Thailand). Known only from the type collection.

Etymology: from Siam, the former name of Thailand.

Macalpinomyces siamensis differs from *Sporisorium coelorachidis*, in which the sori destroy the whole raceme, a columella is present, and the spores are 11-13.5 μm long. The sori of *M. siamensis* are similar to those of *Ustilago gabonensis* Vánky (2006: 39), type on *Phacelurus gabonensis* (Steud.) Clayton (*Rhytachne gabonensis* (Steud.) Hack.), in which the spores are also larger, measuring 8-11 × 8-13 (-14) μm, and sterile cells are lacking.

Aristida is a large, homogenous genus with c. 250 species in the tropics and subtropics. On *Aristida* twelve (+ one?) smut fungi have been recognised (Vánky 2001: 302-312, 2002a: 382-385, 2004b: 173-177). An additional species is:

Sporisorium clandestinum R.G. Shivas, Vánky & Athipunyakom, **sp. nov.**

Typus in matrice Aristida setacea Retz., Thailand, Kalasin Prov., Na Khu Distr., cca. 10 km NW urbe Na Khu, 16°49'03.0" N, 103°57'33.6" E, alt. 320 m.s.m., 20.XII.2005, leg. R.G. Shivas, P. Athipunyakom, S. Likhitekaraj, W. Butranu, C. & K. Vánky. **Holotypus** in Herbario Ustil. Vánky, H.U.V. 21 202; **isotypi** in BPI 872 193, BRIP 47 754 et T.P.P.H. 1753.

Sporisorium clandestinum a specie *Sporisorium inopinatum* Vánky (*Mycotaxon* 81: 384, 2002a; *typus in matrice Aristida scabrivalvis* Hack., Zimbabwe) distinctum, cuius sori item inconspicui, obtecti, imprimis glomerulis sporarum facile separabilibus, sporisque minoribus, rotundis, uniformibus, 5-6,5 × 5,5-7 μm, et pariete crasso (1-2,5 (-3) μm) cellularum sterilium. Glomeruli sporarum speciei *S. inopinatum* semipermanentes, sporae eorum dimorphicae, subpolyedrice irregulares, magnitudine 8-11 × 8-12 (-13) μm, et pariete cellularum sterilium tenue (0,5-1,5 μm).

Sori (Fig. 2) in some ovaries of an inflorescence, inconspicuous, enclosed by the awned lemma except for a slightly protruding, asymmetrically swollen part of the fusiform sorus, 0.5-1 × 3-4 mm, at first covered by a thin, greyish peridium of host origin which ruptures at maturity disclosing the black, semiagglutinated to granular powdery mass of spore balls, spores, and sterile cells. More often, the sori fall off the plants unopened, still enclosed by the lemma. **Spore balls** varying in shape and size, subglobose, ovoid, ellipsoidal, elongated or irregular, 30-70 × 40-80 (-100) μm, dark olivaceous brown to opaque, composed of tens or hundreds of spores which separate easily. **Spores** (Figs 6-7) globose, ovoid, ellipsoidal, 5-6.5 × 5.5-7 μm, olivaceous brown; wall slightly uneven, 0.5-0.8 μm thick, thinner on one side where the spores are slightly paler, surface finely low verrucose, spore profile smooth to finely wavy. **Sterile cells** (Fig. 6) in irregular groups or single, varying in shape and size, globose, ovoid, ellipsoidal, elongated or slightly irregular, 5-10.5 × 6.5-14 (-16) μm, pale yellowish brown; wall even or slightly uneven, 1-2.5 (-3) μm thick, smooth or rough from fine, low, sparse warts.

On Poaceae: *Aristida setacea* Retz.

Distribution: SE Asia (Thailand). Known only from the type collection.

Sporisorium clandestinum differs from the other, similar smut fungi of *Aristida* especially by the hidden sori, the small, rounded, uniform spores (neither polyangular nor polymorphic as in some other species), and by the presence of thick-walled sterile cells between the loose spore balls.

Pseudosorghum A. Camus, in the subfam. Panicoideae, tribe Andropogoneae, subtribe Sorghinae, has two species in tropical Asia. It is closely related to *Sorghum* (Clayton & Renvoize 1986: 340). No smut fungus has been reported on *Pseudosorghum*. The smut fungi of *Sorghum* (including *Sarga*) have been revised by Vánky & Shivas (2001: 339-353) who recognised ten species. A different, new species is:

Fig. 1. Sori of *Macalpinomyces siamensis* in some ovaries of *Coelorachis striata* (type). Habit. Bar = 1 cm. **Fig. 2.** Sori of *Sporisorium clandestinum* in some ovaries of *Aristida setacea* (type). Habit and enlarged an infected and a healthy spikelet. Bars = 1 cm. **Fig. 3.** A sorus of *Sporisorium pseudosorghii* in the inflorescence of *Pseudosorghum fasciculare* (type). Habit and to the left a healthy inflorescence. Bar = 1 cm

Sporisorium pseudosorghii Vánky, R.G. Shivas & Athipunya-kom, sp. nov.

Typus in matrice *Pseudosorghum fasciculare* (Roxb.) A. Camus (det. H. Scholz, B), Thailand, Chaiyaphum Prov., Khon San Distr., 3 km NNW Chulabhorn Dam, 16°02'10.2" N, 101°40'12.1" E, alt. 796 m, 21.XII.2005, leg. R.G., M.D.E., A.J. & G.E. Shivas, P. Athipunya-kom, S. Likhitekaraj, W. Butranu, C. & K. Vánky. *Holotypus* in H.U.V. 21 241; *isotypi* in BRIP 47 732, T.P.P.H. 1759, et in Vánky, Ust. exs. no. 1299.

Sori inflorescentiam totam destruentes, eam in massam 1-1,5 mm latam, usque ad 7-8 cm longam, nigram, pulveream sporarum intermixtam cum cellulis sterilibus transformantes, vagina folii distalis plus-minus obtectam, columellam longam,

centralem, simplicem, tenuiescentem, saepe curvatam vel undulatam, residuam axis florae, raro ad partem eius distalem ramis brevibus instructam circumdantem. *Sporae* maturae singulae, globosae, subglobosae usque plerumque late ellipsoidales, 7-9 × 8-10,5 μm, mediocriter- usque atro-flavidobrunneae; pariete aequali, 0,5-0,8 μm crasso, leniter, dense punctato-verruculoso, imago obliqua sporarum levis. *Cellulae steriles* in catervis irregularibus, cellulae singulae forma et magnitudine variae, subglobosae, ellipsoidales usque plerumque irregulares, cum uno vel nonnullis lateribus deplanatis, 4-12 × 5,5-13 μm, subhyalinae; pariete cca. 0,5 μm crasso, levi.

Sori (Fig. 3) destroying the whole inflorescence transforming it into a 1-1.5 mm wide, up to 7-8 cm long, black,

Figs 4-5. Spores and sterile cells of *Macalpinomyces siamensis* on *Coelorachis striata* in LM and in SEM (type). Figs 6-7. Spores and sterile cells of *Sporisorium clandestinum* on *Aristida setacea* in LM and in SEM (type). Figs 8-9. Spores and sterile cells of *Sporisorium pseudosorghii* on *Pseudosorghum fasciculare* in LM and in SEM (type). Bars = 10 μ m

powdery spore mass intermixed with sterile cells, more or less hidden by the distal leaf sheath, surrounding a long, central, simple, narrowing, often curved or undulate columella, the remnant of the floral axis, rarely with short branches on its distal part. **Spores** (Figs 8-9) when mature single, globose, subglobose to mostly broadly ellipsoidal, 7-9 × 8-10.5 µm, medium to dark yellowish brown; wall even, 0.5-0.8 µm thick, finely, densely punctate-verruculose, spore profile smooth. **Sterile cells** (Figs 8-9) in irregular groups, single cells varying in shape and size, subglobose, ellipsoidal to usually irregular, with one or several flattened sides, 4-12 × 5.5-13 µm, subhyaline; wall c. 0.5 µm thick, smooth.

On Poaceae: *Pseudosorghum fasciculare* (Roxb.) A. Camus.

Distribution: SE Asia (Thailand). Known only from the type locality.

The smut fungi of *Eulalia* and *Eulaliopsis* have been revised by Vánky (2000: 183-186), recognising six species, all in the genus *Sporisorium*. A different, new species is:

Sporisorium trispicatae R.G. Shivas, Vánky & Athipunyakom, sp. nov.

Typus in matrice Eulalia trispicata (Schult.) Henr. (det. H. Scholz, B), Thailand, Chiang Mai Prov., Mae Taeng Distr., Mae Ngad Dam, 19°09'40.5" N, 99°02'24.1" E, alt. 397 m.s.m., 28.XII.2005, leg. R.G. Shivas, P. Athipunyakom, S. Likhitekaraj, W. Butranu, C. & K. Vánky. **Holotypus** in Herbario Ustil. Vánky, H.U.V. 21 200; **isotypus** in BRIP 47 730.

Sporisorium trispicatae distinctum a specie Sorosporium eulaliae L. Ling (Sydowia 7: 155, 1953; = *Sporisorium eulaliae* (L. Ling) Vánky; *typus in matrice Eulalia trispicata*, Australia) *ei maxime propinquo imprimis soris in nonnullis ovariis inflorescentiae eiusdem, glomeruli sporarum majoribus,*

50-140 µm longis et pariete sporarum externarum tenuiore (0,5-1,5 µm). Sori speciei S. eulaliae in spiculis eiusdem inflorescentiae omnibus, glomeruli sporarum 30-90 µm longi et pariete sporarum externarum 1-2 (-2,5) µm crasso.

Sori (Fig. 10, Pl. Ib) in some ovaries of an inflorescence, long cylindrical, narrowing towards the apex, bearing remnants of the style and stigma, c. 1 × 10-30 mm, at first covered by a pale beige peridium which ruptures from its apex or splits longitudinally disclosing the black, granular-powdery mass of spore balls surrounding a long columella. Columella band-like which partly may split into filiform components. **Spore balls** (Figs 13-14) globose, ovoid, ellipsoidal to slightly irregular, 40-90 × 50-140 µm, dark reddish brown, composed of tens or hundreds of spores which separate easily. **Spores** (Figs 13-14) dimorphic; outer spores subglobose, ellipsoidal to slightly subpolyhedrally irregular, 9.5-12 × 10.5-14.5 µm, dark yellowish brown; wall slightly unevenly thickened, 0.5-1.5 µm thick, thickest at the free surface where it is evidently verrucose, warts up to 0.5 or 1 µm high, spore profile smooth to rounded serrulate on the free surface; inner spores globoid or subpolyhedrally slightly irregular, about the size of the outer spores, pale yellowish brown; wall even, c. 0.5 µm thick, apparently smooth or very finely punctate. **Sterile cells** absent.

On Poaceae: *Eulalia trispicata* (Schult.) Henr.

Distribution: SE Asia (Thailand). Known only from the type locality.

Sporisorium trispicatae differs from the closely related *S. eulaliae* (L. Ling) Vánky (type on *Eulalia trispicata*, Australia) by having sori in some ovaries of an inflorescence, larger spore balls, 50-140 µm long, and thinner walls of the outer spores (0.5-1.5 µm). In *S. eulaliae* the sori are in all spikelets of an inflorescence, the spore balls are 30-90 µm long, and the wall of the outer spores is 1-2 (-2.5) µm thick.

Key to the smut fungi (*Sporisorium*) of *Eulalia* and *Eulaliopsis*

- | | | |
|----|---|-----------------------|
| 1 | Spore balls ephemeral; spores uniform; sterile cells present | 2 |
| 1* | Spore balls semipermanent or permanent; spores variable; sterile cells absent | 4 |
| 2 | Spores 5.5-9 µm long | 3 |
| 2* | Spores 9.5-13 µm long | <i>S. pollinianum</i> |
| 3 | Spore wall 1-1.5 µm thick, uneven. On <i>Eulalia</i> | <i>S. guangxiense</i> |
| 3* | Spore wall 0.5 µm thick, even. On <i>Eulaliopsis</i> | <i>S. indicum</i> |
| 4 | Spore balls 25-55 µm long, of few spores (10-40?); spores 8-14 µm long | <i>S. pollinae</i> |
| 4* | Spore balls larger, of more spores; spores larger | 5 |
| 5 | Outer spores up to 20 µm long; spore wall 1-3 µm thick | <i>S. crypticum</i> |
| 5* | Outer spores up to 15 µm long; spore wall thinner | 6 |
| 6 | Sori in some ovaries of an inflorescence; spore wall 0.5-1.5 µm thick | <i>S. trispicatae</i> |
| 6* | Sori in all spikelets of an inflorescence; spore wall 1-2 (-2.5) µm thick | <i>S. eulaliae</i> |

Fig. 10. Sori of *Sporisorium trispicatae* in some ovaries of *Eulalia trispicata* (type). Habit and enlarged a spikelet with a central columella. Bars = 1 cm. Fig. 11. Sori of *Tilletia chiangmaiensis* in some ovaries of *Arundinella bengalensis* (type). Habit. Bar = 1 cm. Fig. 12. Sori of *Tilletia filisora* in some ovaries of *Pennisetum setaceum* (type). Habit and enlarged a spikelet with a sorus. Bars = 1 cm for habit, and 2 mm for the detail drawing

The smut fungi of *Arundinella* have been revised by Vánky (2004a: 88-94) recognising eight species. A further species was described by Shivas & Vánky (2005: 101). On *Arundinella* two species of *Tilletia* are known: *T. arundinellae* L. Ling, type on *A. anomala* Steud., China, and *T. lineata* R.G. Shivas & Vánky, type on *A. nepalensis* Trin., Australia. A different, new species was collected in Thailand on *A. bengalensis*, which is described as:

Tilletia chiangmaiensis R.G. Shivas, Vánky & Athipunyakom, sp. nov.

Typus in matrice Arundinella bengalensis (Spreng.) Druce (det. H. Scholz, B), Thailand, Chiang Mai Prov., Phrao Distr., 53 km NNE urbe Chiang Mai, 19°05'16.2" N, 99°05'43.0" E, alt. 538 m.s.m., 28.XII.2005, leg. R.G. Shivas, P. Athipunyakom, S. Likhitekaraj, W. Butranu, C. & K. Vánky. *Holotypus* in Herbario Ustil. Vánky, H.U.V. 21 197; *isotypus* in BRIP 47 731.

Sori in ovariis nonnullis inflorescentiae eiusdem, longe cylindracei, saepe curvati vel torti, 1-2 × 10-30 mm, peridio

crasso, hispido, primo viride serius brunneo, quo in maturitate longitudinaliter fisso, massam nigram pulveream sporarum cellulis sterilibus intermixtam ostendentes. Sporae globosae, subglobosae usque late ellipsoidales, 19-26,5 × 19-28 μm, atrobadae usque subopacae vel opacae; pariete 1,5-2,5 (-3) μm crasso, cum verrucis vel spinis 1-1,5 (-2) μm altis, in visu superficiali maculis atris, dense distributis, irregulariter polyangularibus apparentibus, in diametro sporae 9-15, in visu opticali mediano 42-62 in circuitu aequatoriali, acutis vel subacutis, in vagina tenui, hyalina inclusis. In SEM verrucae sejunctae, raro tantum 2 vel 3 partim confluentes. Cellulae steriles multae, forma et magnitudine variae, globosae, subglobosae, ellipsoidales usque parum irregulares, 10-28 × 11-36 μm, pallide flavidobrunneae; pariete aequali, 1,5-5,5 μm crasso, leniter usque grosse verruculoso-echinato.

Sori (Fig. 11, Pl. Ic) in some ovaries of an inflorescence, long cylindrical, often curved or twisted, 1-2 × 10-30 mm, covered by a thick, hispid, first green later brown peridium that splits longitudinally at maturity exposing the black, powdery mass of spores intermixed with sterile cells. *Sporae*

(Figs 15-16) globose, subglobose to broadly ellipsoidal, 19-26.5 × 19-28 µm, dark chocolate-brown to subopaque or opaque; wall 1.5-2.5 (-3) µm thick, provided with 1-1.5 (-2) µm high warts or spines, in surface view appearing as densely situated, irregularly polyangular darker spots, 9-15 per spore diameter, in optical median view 42-62 on the equatorial circumference, acute or subacute, embedded in a thin, hyaline sheath. In SEM warts isolated, only rarely 2 or 3

partly confluent. **Sterile cells** (Figs 15-16) numerous, varying in shape and size, globose, subglobose, ellipsoidal to slightly irregular, 10-28 × 11-36 µm, pale yellowish brown; wall even, 1.5-5.5 µm thick, smooth, finely to coarsely verrucose-echinulate.

On Poaceae: *Arundinella bengalensis* (Spreng.) Druce.

Distribution: SE Asia (Thailand). Known only from the type collection.

Key to the *Tilletia* species of *Arundinella*

- 1 Sori 10-30 µm long, hispid; spores with 1-1.5 (-2) µm high warts *T. chiangmaiensis*
 1* Sori up to 5 mm long, smooth; spores with higher warts 2
 2 Sori ovoid, without longitudinal stripes; spores 22-33 (-37) µm long, with 1.5-3 µm high warts *T. arundinellae*
 2* Sori obovoid, with two longitudinal stripes; spores 20-27 (-30) µm long, with 1.5-2.5 µm high warts *T. lineata*

Vánky (2003b: 8-20, 2006: 43) studied the smut fungi of *Pennisetum* and recognised 14 species. Between them there is one *Tilletia* species, *T. barclayana* (Bref.) Sacc. & P. Syd., with its synonyms *T. pennisetina* Syd. and *T. ajrekari* Mundk. Its spores are globose to broadly ellipsoidal, 20-25.5 × 20-25.5 (-27) µm (including ornamentation), reddish brown to subopaque; wall 3-4.5 µm thick, provided with densely situated, truncate, 1.5-3 µm long, polyangular warts. A new, different species is:

Tilletia filisora R.G. Shivas, Vánky & Athipunyakom, sp. nov.

Typus in matrice *Pennisetum setosum* (Swartz) L.C. Rich., Thailand, Phitsanulok Prov., Wan Thong Distr., cca. 52 km E urbe Phitsanulok, 16°51'42.9" N, 100°41'31.8" E, alt. 509 m.s.m., 23.XII.2005, leg. R.G., M.D.E., A.J. & G.E. Shivas, P. Athipunyakom, S. Likhitekaraj, W. Butranu, C. & K. Vánky. **Holotypus** in Herbario Ustil. Vánky, H.U.V. 21 164; **isotypus** in BRIP 47 729. **Paratypus** in matrice *Pennisetum setosum*, Thailand, Chaiyaphum Prov., Khon San Distr., cca. 15 km E Chulaphorn Dam, 16°30'02.5" N, 101°48'29.1" E, alt. 477 m.s.m., 21.XII.2005, leg. R.G., M.D.E., A.J. & G.E. Shivas, P. Athipunyakom, S. Likhitekaraj, W. Butranu, C. & K. Vánky, H.U.V. 21 165, **isoparatypus** in BRIP 47 746.

Sori in ovariis nonnullis eiusdem inflorescentiae, inconspicui, anguste cylindrici, fere filiformes, 0,3-0,7 × 2-6 mm, involucris floralibus plus-minus absconditi, peridio tenui, persistenti, cinereo, origine nutritorio cooperiti, quo in maturitate apice longitudinaliter fissio massa primo agglutinata serius pulverea sporarum cellularumque sterilium liberata. **Sporae** forma, magnitudine, colore, ornamentatione valde variae, globosae, ovoideae, ellipsoidales usque subpolyedrice parum irregulares, 12-20 × 13-24 µm, flavido- usque atrobadias vel etiam subopacae; pariete aequali, 2-3,5 µm crasso, leniter verrucoso usque plerumque verrucis 1-2,5 µm altis, irregularibus, apice deplanatis vel rotundis. Verrucae in

visu superficiali sicut maculae rotundatae usque plerumque irregulariter polyangulares, atrae, in diametro sporae 8-16, in circumferentia aequatoriali 25-45 earum. Cellulae steriles forma et magnitudine variae, globosae, ellipsoidales usque irregulares, 8-22 × 9,5-23 (-30) µm, subhyalinae usque pallide flavidobrunneae; pariete 1-2,5 µm crasso, levi usque leniter verrucoso-echinulato.

Sori (Fig. 12, Pl. Id) in some ovaries of an inflorescence, inconspicuous, narrow cylindrical, nearly filiform, 0.3-0.7 × 2-6 mm, mostly hidden by the floral envelopes, covered by a thin, persistent, greyish peridium of host origin the apex of which splits longitudinally at maturity disclosing the black, first agglutinated, later powdery mass of spores and sterile cells. The sori mature from their distal part where the spores are scattered, leaving behind the thin, ruptured, tubiform peridium, whereas the basal part of the sori contains still agglutinated spore masses. **Spores** (Figs 17-18) much varying in shape, size, colour, and ornamentation, globose, ovoid, ellipsoidal to subpolyhedrally slightly irregular, 12-20 × 13-24 µm, yellowish- to dark chocolate-brown, or even subopaque; wall even, 2-3.5 µm thick, from finely verrucose to usually possessing 1-2.5 µm high, irregular warts with flattened or rounded tips. Warts in surface view appear as rounded to usually irregularly polyangular, darker spots, 8-16 per spore diameter, 25-45 on the equatorial circumference. **Sterile cells** (Figs 17-18) varying in shape and size, globose, ellipsoidal to irregular, 8-22 × 9.5-23 (-30) µm, subhyaline to pale yellowish brown; wall 1-2.5 µm thick, smooth to finely verrucose-echinulate.

On Poaceae: *Pennisetum setosum* (Swartz) L.C. Rich.

Distribution: SE Asia (Thailand). Known from several collections.

Typical for *Tilletia filisora* are the narrow, nearly filiform sori, and the greatly varying shape, size, colour, and ornamentation of both the spores and sterile cells.

Figs 13-14. Spore balls and spores of *Sporisorium trispicatae* on *Eulalia trispicata* in LM and in SEM (type). Figs 15-16. Spores and sterile cells of *Tilletia Chiangmaiensis* on *Arundinella bengalensis* in LM and in SEM (type). Figs 17-18. Spores and sterile cells of *Tilletia filisora* on *Pennisetum setaceum* in LM and in SEM (type). Bars = 10 μ m

The smut fungi of *Hyparrhenia* have been revised by Vánky (2003a), who recognised twelve species, including one species of *Tilletia*, *T. hyparrheniae* Ling, type on *Hyparrhenia subplumosa* Stapf, from Sierra Leone. It has oblong sori with tapering ends, c. 1.5-2 × 10 mm, covered by a rather thick, brownish, persistent peridium. The spores are (22-) 26-32 (-36) µm long, dark olive-brown to subopaque, densely ornamented with 0.8-1.5 wide, 2.5-4 µm long warts with blunt tip. A different, new species is:

Tilletia lageniformis Vánky, C. Vánky, R.G. Shivas & Athipunyakom, sp. nov.

Typus in matrice *Hyparrhenia rufa* (Nees) Stapf, Thailand, Chiang Mai Prov., Mae Taeng Distr., Mae Ngad Dam, 19°09'40.5" N, 99°02'24.1" E, alt. 397 m.s.m., 28.XII.2005, leg. R.G. Shivas, P. Athipunyakom, S. Likhitekaraj, W. Butranu, C. & K. Vánky. *Holotypus* in Herbario Ustil. Vánky, H.U.V. 21 167, *isotypi* in BRIP 47 749 et in BPI 872 194. *Paratypus in matrice* *Hyparrhenia rufa*, Thailand, Chiang Mai Prov., Phrao Distr., 57 km NNE urbe Chiang Mai, 19°04'27.0" N, 99°07'20.5" E, alt. 397 m.s.m., 28.XII.2005, leg. R.G. Shivas, P. Athipunyakom, S. Likhitekaraj, W. Butranu, C. & K. Vánky, H.U.V. 21 168; *isoparatypus* in BRIP 47 750.

Sori in ovarii nonnullis eiusdem inflorescentiae inconspicui, inter involucria floralia expansa apparentes, recenter plerumque lageniformes, in statu siccitatis saepe ovoidei, late subfusiformes, ellipsoideales vel cylindrici, 0,8-2 × 2-5 mm, primo peridio tenue, persistenti, cinereo, origine nutritorio cooperti. In statu maturitatis apice peridii fissis massa nigra, pulverea sporarum et cellularum sterilium per exitum successive dispersa quia massa agglutinata sporarum basipetaliter maturescens et pulverescens. Sporae globosae, subglobosae, late ellipsoideales vel subpolyedricae irregulares, 18-25 × 18,5-27 µm, mediocriter usque atro-badiae vel opacae; pariete aequali, 2-3 µm crasso, verrucis 1-2,5 µm altis, irregularibus cum apice deplanato vel rotundato instructis. Verrucae in visu superficiali sicut maculae atrae, rotundae vel usque plerumque irregulariter polyangulares apparentes, 12-17 per diametrum sporae, 41-54 in circumferentia aequatoriali. In SEM verrucae frequenter in seriebus ordinatae paribus intervallis cum circulo 'aequatoriali', sed ad 2 areas polares, oppositas sejunctae manentes. Cellulae steriles globosae, ellipsoideales usque parum irregulares, 10,5-30 × 11-35 µm, subhyalinae usque pallide flavidobrunneae; pariete 1-3 µm crasso, levi, leniter usque crasse, dense verrucosae.

Sori (Fig. 19, Pl. Ie) in some ovaries of an inflorescence, inconspicuous, visible between the spreading floral envelopes, mostly flask-shaped when fresh, often ovoid, broadly subfusiform, ellipsoidal or cylindrical when dried, 0.8-2 × 2-5 mm, first covered by a thin, persistent greyish peridium of host origin the apex of which fissures at maturity and the black, powdery mass of spores and sterile cells is successively dispersed through the opening as the agglutinated mass of spores matures basipetally and becomes powdery. *Spores* (Figs 21-22) globose, subglobose, broadly ellipsoidal or subpolyhedrally irregular, 18-25 × 18.5-27 µm, medium to dark chocolate-brown or opaque; wall even, 2-3 µm thick,

provided with 1-2.5 µm high, irregular warts with flattened or rounded tips. Warts in surface view appear as rounded to usually irregularly polyangular, darker spots, 12-17 per spore diameter, 41-54 on the equatorial circumference. In SEM warts often arranged in rows, parallel with an 'equatorial' circle, but they remain isolated at the two opposite 'polar' areas. *Sterile cells* (Fig. 21) globose, ellipsoidal to slightly irregular, 10.5-30 × 11-35 µm, subhyaline to pale yellowish brown; wall 1-3 µm thick, smooth, finely to coarsely, densely verrucose.

On Poaceae: *Hyparrhenia rufa* (Nees) Stapf.

Distribution: SE Asia (Thailand). Known only from the type collections.

Etymology: from the Latin *lageniformis*, -e = flask-shaped, referring to the form of the fresh sori, with a wide, globoid or ellipsoidal basal part, contracted into a shorter or longer, narrow, cylindrical distal part.

The genus *Yelsemia* J. Walker (2001: 225) was erected for a curious smut fungus of two *Arthropodium* species (Anthericaceae, Liliaceae s. lat.), from Australia, with unusual spore morphology (comp. also Vánky 2002b: 182-183). It belongs to the order Urocystales R. Bauer & Oberw. Two species have been subsequently added, *Y. speculariae* (J.A. Stev.) Vánky & R. Bauer (in Vánky 2002a: 428) on *Triodanis perfoliata* (L.) Nieuwl. (*Specularia perfoliata* (L.) DC., Campanulaceae), USA, and *Y. lowrieana* R.G. Shivas & Vánky (2003: 132) on *Byblis rorida* Lowrie & Conran (Byblidaceae), Australia. A smut fungus in the capsules of *Drosera burmanni* (Droseraceae) from Thailand, with spores typical for the genus *Yelsemia*, is described as a new species:

Yelsemia droserae R.G. Shivas, Vánky & Athipunyakom, sp. nov.

Typus in matrice: *Drosera burmanni* Vahl, Thailand, Sri Saket Prov., Non Khun Distr., 42 km SSW urbe Ubon Ratchatani, 14°52'59.4" N, 104°42'30.9" E, alt. 152 m.s.m., 18.XII.2005, leg. R.G. Shivas, P. Athipunyakom, S. Likhitekaraj, W. Butranu, C. & K. Vánky. *Holotypus* in H.U.V. 21 188; *isotypus* in BRIP 47 734. *Paratypus* on *Drosera indica* L. (det. A. Lowrie, Nedlands, Western Australia), Australia, Northern Territory, 40 km W urbe Jabiru, Arnhem Highway, 12°41'40.0" S, 132°27'10.1" E, alt. 22 m.s.m., 11.VI.2006, leg. M.J. Ryley, M.D.E. & R.G. Shivas, BRIP 47 947; *isoparatypus* H.U.V. 21 358.

Sori in capsulis omnibus eiusdem inflorescentiae, semina destruentes, tumefacti, globoidei, diametro cca. 1,5-2 mm, atro-nigrobrunnei. Capsulae in maturitate longitudinaliter fissae, in pluribus partibus dehiscentes massam nigram, pulveream sporarum ostendentes. Sporae globoideae, parum depressae, in visu laterali subcirculares vel late ellipticae, 25-33 µm latae, aequatorialiter atrobunneae, 20-28 µm latitudine fasciatae, et in lateribus deplanatis 2 operculis oppositis, polaribus, tumefactis, convexis usque semiglobosis, pallide flavis, 3-7 µm altis, 12-20 µm latis instructae. Sporae in visu faciali circulares, ellipticae, ovoideae usque parum subpolyangulariter irregulares, 25-33,5 × 28-38 µm, atrobunneae usque subopacae, operculis polaribus

Fig. 19. Sori of *Tilletia lageniformis* in some ovaries of *Hyparrhenia rufa* (type). Habit and enlarged a spikelet with a sorus. Bars = 1 cm for habit, and 3 mm for the detail drawing. Fig. 20. Sori of *Yelsemia droserae* in the capsules of *Drosera burmanni* (type). Habit and enlarged a swollen capsule filled with spores. Bars = 1 cm for habit, and 1 mm for the detail drawing

Figs 21-22. Spores and sterile cells of *Tilletia lageniformis* on *Hyparrhenia rufa* in LM and in SEM (type). Figs 23-24. Spores of *Yelsemia droserae* on *Drosera burmanni* in LM and in SEM (type). Bars = 10 µm

Pl. I. Sori of new smut fungi from Thailand. Fig. a. A sorus of *Macalpinomyces siamensis* in the ovary of *Coelorachis striata* (type). Fig. b. Sori of *Sporisorium trispicatae* in some ovaries of *Eulalia trispicata* (type). Fig. c. A sorus of *Tilletia Chiangmaiensis* in the ovary of *Arundinella bengalensis* (type). Fig. d. A sorus of *Tilletia filisora* in the ovary of *Pennisetum setaceum* (type). Fig. e. A sorus of *Tilletia lageniformis* in the ovary of *Hyparrhenia rufa* (type). Fig. f. Sori of *Yelsmia droserae* in the capsules of *Drosera burmanni* (type)

congruenter cum area circulari, centrali, pallidior; pariete spora in fascia aequatoriali 1,5-3 µm crasso, parum tenuiore sub areis polaribus (1-1,5 µm), leniter, dense verruculoso; imago obliqua sporarum leniter aspera.

Sori (Fig. 20, Pl. If) in all capsules of an inflorescence, destroying the seeds, swollen, globoid, c. 1.5-2 mm in diameter, dark blackish brown. At maturity the capsules split longitudinally in several places, disclosing the black, powdery mass of spores. **Spores** (Figs 23-24) globoid, slightly flattened, in side view subcircular or broadly elliptic, 25-33 µm wide, with a dark brown equatorial band, 20-28 µm wide, and two opposite, swollen, convex to semiglobose, pale yellow polar caps on the flattened sides, 3-7 µm high, 12-20 µm wide. Spores in face view circular, elliptic, ovoid to subpolyangularly slightly irregular, 25-33.5 × 28-38 µm, dark brown to subopaque with a circular paler central area corresponding to the polar caps; spore wall of the equatorial

band 1.5-3 µm thick, slightly thinner (1-1.5 µm) beneath the polar areas, finely, densely verruculose, spore profile finely rough.

On Droseraceae: *Drosera burmanni* Vahl., *D. indica* L.

Distribution: SE Asia (Thailand), Australia.

The spores of *Yelsemia droserae* are the same size as those of *Y. lowrieana*. The two species differ however, i.e., in sorus morphology, in the thickness of the spore wall at the equatorial band and in host plant taxonomy. In *Y. lowrieana* the sori are in the stems, flowers, and glands, and usually have a polycystic structure, the spore wall is 2.5-4 µm thick, and the host plant belongs to the family Byblidaceae.

The recent discovery of *Y. droserae* in Australia on a second species of *Drosera*, shows that the smut is not host specific and further indicates that it is widely distributed, comprising at least S & SE Asia, Indonesia, and Australasia.

Key to the species of *Yelsemia*

- 1 Sori in the capsules (seeds) only 2
 1* Sori in stems, flowers, and seeds 3
 2 Spores 22-29 µm long; equatorial band 12-21 µm wide. On *Triodanis* *Y. speculariae*
 2* Spores 28-38 µm long; equatorial band 20-28 µm wide. On *Drosera* *Y. droserae*
 3 Spores 20-25 µm long; equatorial band 12-18 µm wide. On *Arthropodium* *Y. arthropodii*
 3* Spores 28-38 µm long; equatorial band 14-21 µm wide. On *Byblis* *Y. lowrieana*

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